

**MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT AND CONFLICT
RESOLUTION SKILLS OF SECONDARY
SCHOOL ADOLESCENTS:
A CORRELATIONAL STUDY**

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Abstract

The initial inspiration for this study started with the reading from the NCF-2005 which conveys that the main goal of mathematics education in schools is the mathematisation of the child's thinking. Mathematics education tends to develop among its student: formal problem solving, use of heuristics, estimation and approximation, optimisation, use of patterns, visualisation, representation, reasoning and proof, making connections, mathematical communication.

Adolescence is the period of great stress and strain. Adolescent students face various types of conflicts and stressful situation. Conflicts are inevitable for the adolescent but the key is the constructive resolution of them.

Mathematics as a subject from its nature seems to judge a greater conflict resolver in a student having good mathematics knowledge and understanding. The study thus here tries to find out this interrelationship between the two variables namely "achievement in mathematics" and "conflict resolution skill". The sample of this study has been adolescents of class IX and XII of a school comprising of 143 students in total. The tool developed by the investigator on conflict resolution skills has been administered on the students and for achievement data their last terminal examination score in mathematics were collected.

The analysis of the collected data revealed that there is an overall positive correlation between the two variables under the study. It was also found out although there was significant higher correlation between the two variables for some identified dimensions of conflict resolution skills but overall correlation value is not high enough to be called significant. Finally the paper concludes with a discussion on the findings and the follow up studies.

Key Words: Mathematics Achievement, Adolescents, Conflict, Adolescents' Conflict, Conflict Resolution Skills

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics as it goes is an essential curricular input to the school going children. Secondary school children passing through the early grades which cover the beginning foundations of math are exposed to higher level of mathematics which includes algebra, geometry and analysis, trigonometry, etc. Mathematics is an essential subject for the youth for its immense application in their daily life. The main goal of mathematics in school is the mathematisation of the child's thought processes NCF(2005). In the words of David Wheeler, it is "more useful to know how to mathematise than to know a lot of mathematics". Learning math improves the child's *problem solving skills*. Even as a very young elementary school student they develop the ability to solve problems by learning to calculate simple arithmetic problems, such as one plus one. Every new math level they tackle requires them to expand the ability to dissect a problem and solve each individual part. They can apply this to their life as they get older. Even in relationship building, problems often need to be broken down into sections to get to the core problem and solution. Not every child wants to be a mathematician. However, all children can benefit from strong math skills. The problem solving processes used in mathematics classes develop logic skills. The trial and error required to solve math problems is useful in science and statistics. Taking the time to work through math problems and arrive at the correct answer teaches your child persistence and perseverance. Outside of school, activities children engage in such as crafts, tinkering with electronics or cooking, all indirectly relate to the problem solving abilities learned in math class.

Mathematics is a subject that deals with logic, decision-making, deductions, assumptions, precision, clarity of thought and the ability to solve problems in a calculative manner by following a series of steps. This is an important subject not only from the point of view of getting an academic qualification at school or college, but is also a subject that prepares us for the future as well, irrespective of

which walk of life we choose to be a part of. There are different branches of mathematics that have a wide range of practical applications, such as algebra, geometry, trigonometry, calculus and the basic commercial applications of mathematics such as statistics, computing and concepts like addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, percentages, ratios and proportions, fractions, profit and loss, calculation of simple interest, etc. Lynn(2011).

Adolescence is the period of great stress and strain. Adolescent students face various types of conflicts and stressful situations. There are various classifications of adolescent conflict based upon the findings of different educationists and researchers. The various problems related to teen years can be related to their education, health, empowerment, employment, drug abuse, leisure time activities, etc. In this study the conflicts of adolescents are kept under four broad categories, i.e. arising within the individual (*intrapersonal*), with the student and their friend (*interpersonal*), or within his/her friend circle (*intra group*) or with some other member(s) of the society (*intergroup*). The adolescent at this time deal with immense pressure and pass through severe conflicting situations related to their education, career choices, and problem with friends, family, and other members of society. Teenage is the year of great stress and strain and it is always worthy to come out of these stress and strain for an effective future life. Thus there is always a need for the adolescent to develop skills by which they can fight with the conflict they are confronted with. Conflicts are inevitable for the adolescent but the key is the constructive resolution of them. The adolescent must be skilled enough so that they can take responsibility for making healthier choices, resisting negative pressures and avoiding risk behaviour. Effective acquisition of these skills can influence the way adolescents cope up with stress and face the challenges present in their lives. There is an unending list of key skills important to overcome the conflicts faced by the adolescents. However, they may be categorised into certain specific dimensions such as self focussed resolution skills and support seeking resolution skills, etc. within which we may further include self awareness, critical thinking and analysis, effective decision making and mediation, facilitation, etc. These skills can be

used for resolving conflicts of all types such as intra-personal or interpersonal and intra-group or intergroup conflicts etc among the adolescents.

Mathematics as a subject from its nature seems to be a greater conflict resolver in a student having good mathematics knowledge and understanding. Various studies have also shown that good mathematician has better logical reasoning, visualisation and perception ability which are essentials for being able to resolve any conflict constructively. The study thus here tries to find out this interrelationship between the two variables namely "achievement in mathematics" and "conflict resolution skill". The study conducted by Chen, Xinyin; Rubin, Kenneth H.; Li, Dan(1997) finds out relationship between academic achievement and social adjustment. Information on academic achievement and indexes of social adjustment, including social competence, aggression, social inhibition, leadership, and peer acceptance, was collected from multiple sources. It was found that academic achievement predicted children's social competence and peer acceptance. In turn, children's social functioning and adjustment, including social competence, aggression-disruption, leadership, and peer acceptance, uniquely contributed to academic achievement. These results generally supported the "reciprocal effects" model concerning the relations between academic achievement and social adjustment (S. P. Hinshaw, 1992). (PsycINFO Database Record (c) 2012 APA, all rights reserved). Xin Ma and Nand Kishor(1997) conducted a meta-analysis integrated 143 primary studies on the relationship of attitude toward self and social factors with achievement in mathematics. Attitude was decomposed into self-concept about mathematics, perception of family support, and perception of mathematics as a male domain. Major findings included: (a) self-concept, family support, and mathematics as a male domain were all related to achievement; (b) the three relationships did not show significant gender differences; (c) the three relationships consistently decreased from the junior high grades to the senior high grades; (d) the relationship between self-concept and achievement varied as a function of ethnicity, whereas the relationship between family support and achievement was consistent across ethnic

background; (e) the three relationships all varied across sample selection; (f) the relationship between self-concept and achievement varied with sample size, whereas the relationships of family support and mathematics as a male domain with achievement were sample-size invariant; (g) the relationship between self-concept and achievement increased over time, whereas the relationships of family support and mathematics as a male domain with achievement remained almost unchanged over time; and (h) there were no statistically significant interaction effects among gender, grade, and ethnicity for any of the three relationships.

These studies have immensely motivated the researcher to take over this study.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the present study were as follows:

1. To study the relationship of mathematics achievement and conflict resolution skills among the adolescent students.
2. To study the relationship of mathematics achievement and conflict resolution skills among the adolescent students of different classes.
3. To study the relationship of mathematics achievement and different dimensions of conflict resolution skills among the adolescent students.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study in the light of the aforesaid objectives.

1. Adolescent students will have positive correlation between mathematics achievement and conflict resolution skills.
2. Adolescent students of different classes (IX/X) will have positive correlation between mathematics achievement and conflict resolution skills.
3. Adolescent students will have positive correlation between mathematics achievement and different dimensions of conflict resolution skills.

METHODOLOGY

Design

The present study is a correlational study which examines the relationship between mathematics achievement and conflict resolution skills of adolescent students. The study has tried to establish whether and to what degree, relationships exist between the two variables.

Sample

The subjects for the study were the students of class IX and class XII of Atreyee DAV Public School, Balurgaht, W.B. Both the sections of class IX i.e. section A and B were taken for the study. Similarly for class XII both the streams i.e. science and commerce students were taken for the study. The details of the sample of the present study is given in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Details of the Sample

DETAILS OF SAMPLE Name of the School	Name of the Class with section/stream	Number of students studied
Atreyee DAV Public School, Balurghat, West Bengal	IX-A	37
	IX-B	38
	XII-Science	36
	XII-Commerce	32
	Total	143

Tools

The tools that was used in the study was **CONFLICT RESOLUTION SCALE FOR ADOLESCENTS (CRSA)**. The researcher has used a conflict resolution skills scale for measuring adolescent skills in dealing with the upcoming conflict. This test was a Likert-type scale developed by the researcher himself with the help of experts. This conflict resolution skill scale was based upon items in the form of responses, activities or actions an adolescent will take when confronted with a conflicting situation to make him/ her come out of the situation or to make him feel better. These conflict resolution skills are divided here in five dimensions, namely Self Focussed Resolution Skills (**SFRS**), Conflict Resolution

Restructuring Skills (**CRRS**), Conflict Withdrawal and Distraction Skills (**CWDS**), Group Conflict Resolution Skills (**GCRS**), Support Seeking Resolution Skills (**SSRS**).

Procedure

The adolescents in this study were administered to the CRSA and for gathering data for the mathematics achievement their last terminal exams marks in mathematics were collected for the analysis of the data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

ANALYSIS OF CORRELATION IN MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT AND CONFLICT RESOLUTION SKILLS AMONG ADOLESCENTS

Testing Hypothesis-1

- Adolescent students will have positive correlation between mathematics achievement and conflict resolution skills

To test the above hypothesis Spearman Rank Order Correlation was found out for all the students and the results can be summarised in the following Table 2

Table 2: Analysis results on Hypothesis 1 Test

Spearman Rank order Correlation-Ungrouped Data	
Statistic	Value
Correlation (Not corrected)	0.4207
Correlation (Corrected)	0.4187

The above value of correlation 0.418 is positive and hypothesis is accepted. Hence it can be said that mathematics achievement and conflict resolution skills are moderately correlated and the correlation is significant.

ANALYSIS OF CLASS WISE RELATIONSHIP OF MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT AND CONFLICT RESOLUTION SKILLS AMONG THE ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

Testing Hypothesis-2

- Adolescent students will of different classes (IX/X) have positive correlation between mathematics achievement and conflict resolution skills.

To test the above hypothesis Spearman Rank Order Correlation was found out for all the students of class IX and XII separately and the results can be summarised in the following Table 3.

Table 3 : Analysis results on Hypothesis 2 Test

Analysis results for Class IX	Spearman Rank order Correlation-Ungrouped Data	
	Statistic	Value
	Correlation (Not corrected)	0.3750
	Correlation (Corrected)	0.3734
Analysis results for Class XII	Spearman Rank order Correlation-Ungrouped Data	
	Statistic	Value
	Correlation (Not corrected)	0.6524
	Correlation (Corrected)	0.6421

The analysis above reveals that where class IX students' mathematics achievement is moderately correlated to their conflict resolution skills, class XII students' mathematics achievement is highly correlated to their conflict resolution skills. Thus the hypothesis can be rejected.

RELATIONSHIP OF MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT AND DIFFERENT DIMENSIONS OF CONFLICT RESOLUTION SKILLS AMONG THE ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

Testing Hypothesis-3

- Adolescent students will have positive correlation between mathematics achievement and different dimensions of conflict resolution skills.

To test the above hypothesis Spearman Rank Order Correlation was found out for all the students and for the different dimensions of conflict resolution skills the results can be summarised in the following Table 4.

Table 4: Analysis results on Hypothesis 3 Test

DIMENSIONS OF CRSA	ANALYSIS RESULTS	
Self Focussed Resolution Skills (SFRS)	Spearman Rank order Correlation-Ungrouped Data	
	Statistic	Value
	Correlation (Not corrected)	0.7671
	Correlation (Corrected)	0.7661
Conflict Resolution Restructuring Skills (CRRS)	Spearman Rank order Correlation-Ungrouped Data	
	Statistic	Value
	Correlation (Not corrected)	0.7956
	Correlation (Corrected)	0.7945
Conflict Withdrawal and Distraction Skills (CWDS)	Spearman Rank order Correlation-Ungrouped Data	
	Statistic	Value
	Correlation (Not corrected)	0.4236
	Correlation (Corrected)	0.4210
Group Conflict Resolution Skills (GCRS)	Spearman Rank order Correlation-Ungrouped Data	
	Statistic	Value
	Correlation (Not corrected)	0.4790
	Correlation (Corrected)	0.4771
Support Seeking Resolution Skills (SSRS)	Spearman Rank order Correlation-Ungrouped Data	
	Statistic	Value
	Correlation (Not corrected)	0.4993
	Correlation (Corrected)	0.4976

The above table reveals that all the dimensions of conflict resolution skills are positively correlated to mathematics achievement. If the observation is done minutely it can be observed that although for the CWDS, GCRS and SSRS dimension of conflict resolution skills scale, it is moderately correlated to mathematics achievement for the SFRS and CRRS dimension of conflict it is highly correlated to mathematics achievement and thus hypothesis is accepted.

Findings and Discussion

The above analysis shows that as hypothesized in this experiment the analysis results follows. The first outcome on the study suggests that the overall conflict resolution is positively correlated to the achievement in mathematics and the correlation is very moderate which is quite in accordance with the assumed hypothesis. However it is also revealed that the correlation in the early adolescents (IX) is much less than the correlation in the later stage of adolescents (XII) which is very high. These changes may be attributed to the development of higher mathematical skills in the higher classes among the adolescents. As students moves to higher classes they are

expose to higher and complex areas of mathematics which helps them to develop more reasoning, visualization, abstract thinking and logical thinking abilities. These abilities are essential inputs for resolving a conflict. Further it can also be seen that for dimension wise analysis the correlation for all the involved dimensions of CRSA is positive. The higher positive value of correlation in Self Focused Resolution Strategies (SFRS) and Conflict Resolution Restructuring Skills (CRRS) can be attributed to its more problem oriented and logical reasoning nature which is the natural characteristics of a better mathematics student. The remaining three dimensions again reflect the overall trend with its positive correlation to the mathematical ability.

Conclusion

Adolescence is often described, as an exciting transitory phase in the human life cycle but is perhaps the most challenging stage as well. This is a time when adolescents evolve into adults with newly discovered independence and renewed responsibilities. They are constantly in search of their own new identity. They tend to question and appreciate the values of the adult world and try to assert their identity. During adolescence they develop skills that will help them to grow into caring and responsible adults. Adolescence period is a phase of students' life when he is at the secondary stage. It is at this stage that Mathematics comes to the student as an academic discipline. Mathematics is a subject which is very much problem oriented and teaches the ways to resolve those problems. At the secondary stage, the student begins to perceive the structure of mathematics. Mathematical terminology is highly stylised, self-conscious and rigorous. The findings of this study indicate that at the secondary stage, a special emphasis on experimentation and exploration may be worthwhile. Mathematics laboratories are a recent phenomenon, which hopefully will expand considerably in future. Activities in practical mathematics help students immensely in visualization which will further help in resolving their own conflicts.

As we already know that the main goal of mathematics education in schools should be the mathematisation of the child's thinking. Clarity of thought and pursuing assumptions to logical conclusions

is central to the mathematical enterprise. There are many ways of thinking, and the kind of thinking one learns in mathematics is an ability to handle abstractions, and an approach to problem solving. Mathematics as a subject thus seems to develop skills among the adolescents to become an effective adult and a responsible citizen. It is the task of the school administration as well as the teacher to integrate some conflict resolving lessons into the mathematics class so as to make them better individual. Mathematics has lots of scope to help students' to understand themselves better and to socialise in a better way, it is the teacher and parents who have to make them realise how it can be useful to their daily life. The teacher has to take many action plans based on their own designed action research on how to implement mathematics models in resolving the adolescents' conflict.

References

- Cawelti, G.(1993).*Current school practices: Trends and Issues*. New Jersey,Columbia: Prentice Hall publication.
- Chen, Xinyin; Rubin, Kenneth H.; Li, Dan.(1997). Relation between academic achievement and social adjustment: Evidence from Chinese children. *Developmental Psychology*, Vol 33(3), May 1997, 518-525.
- Cobb, P., Confrey, J., diSeva, A., Lehrer, R., and Schauble, L.(2003).Design experiments in educational research, *Educational Research*, 32(1), pp.9-13.
- Cohen, R.(1995). School mathematics and its learning implications. *Adolescent Education*,4(3),pp.43-49.
- Dewey, J. (1913). *Interest and Effort in Education*, Boston, New York and Chicago: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Hill, K.T. (1972). Anxiety in the evaluative context. In W.W. Hartup(Ed.), *The Young Child*,2, pp.225-263. Washington, DC: National Association for Education of young Children.
- Indian Education Commission. (1964). New Delhi, Ministry of Education and Youth Service.
- Johnson,D.W., Johnson,R.T.(1996). Conflict resolution and peer mediation programs in elementary and secondary schools:

A review of the research. Review of Educational Research.
Sage publication.

- Kemp,S.V.(1998).Mathematics learning in elementary schools.
Journal of Social Science,54(2),pp.56-60.
- Laursen, B(1994). Interpersonal conflict during adolescence.
Psychological Bulletin.
- Lynn,D.(2011). The Importance of Children Learning Mathematics
- Ma,X. & Kishore,N(1997). Assessing the Relationship between
Attitude toward Mathematics and Achievement in
Mathematics: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal for Research in
Mathematics Education.* Vol. 28, No. 1 (Jan., 1997), pp. 26-47.
- Meece, L.J., Wigfield A., and Eccles S.J. (1990). Predictors of maths
anxiety and its influence on young adolescents course
enrolment intention and performance in mathematics,
Journal of Educational Psychology, 82(1), pp.66-70.
- MHRD.(1986). "National Policy on Education" , New Delhi.
- NCERT.2005. "National Curriculum Framework-2005", New
Delhi.
- NCERT (2005). Position paper:National focus group On Education
for peace . New Delhi.Offer, O. and Offer, J. B. (1975), *From
Teenage to Young Manhood. A Psychological Study*, Basic
Books, New York.
- NCERT (2010).Ways to Peace: A resource book for teachers.
Department of educational psychology and foundation of
education. NCERT.New Delhi.
- NCERT(2006). Training Course on Peace Education for Teachers.
New Delhi
- Schiefile, U. and Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1995). Motivation and ability
factor in mathematics experience and achievement, *Journal
for Research in Mathematics Educational, 26(2),pp. 163-181.*
- Skemp, R. (1971). *The Psychology of Learning Mathematics*, Hillsade,
NJ: American Financing.
- Smetana JG. Adolescents' and parents' reasoning about actual
family conflict. *Child Development.* 1989; 60:1052-1067.

Sprague, J.R., Sugai, G., and Walker, H. (1998). Anti-social Behaviour in Schools. In T.S. Watson and F.M. Gresham (Eds.), *Handbook of Child Behaviour Therapy* (pp. 451-474). New York: Plenum.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.(2001) . *Learning the Way of Peace: A Teachers' Guide to Peace Education*. New Delhi,UNESCO.

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